

TRAFFIC RULES THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Yu.R.Jumayev

Senior teacher

“Management of preschool education” department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10404100>

Abstract: The article examines the digitization of all aspects of our life, including the role of digital technologies in preschool education, and the problems of modern education. The importance of digital technologies in preschool education, the requirements for their rational and effective use are presented. The article discusses the current problems of the theory and methodology of the use of information and communication technologies and digital technologies as a means of the modern educational process that increases the cognitive activity, outlook and motivation of children of preschool and primary school age, which is considered an important need of the current era of globalization. It is said that the use of digital technologies in the process of education and upbringing guarantees the achievements of preschool children.

Keywords : Digital technologies , information from computer technologies, traffic rules, mobile applications, Animation, slide presentations, movies, Road traffic accidents.

The socio-economic changes taking place in the Republic of Uzbekistan have led to serious changes in the education system, in particular, in the pre-school education section. In the context of digital transformation, these changes have affected the organizational and substantive aspects of preschool education. On January 9, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the meeting dedicated to the development of information and communication technologies, noted that "the development of information technologies and communications serves the rapid development of all areas, creates comfort for people." It should also be noted that during the development of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program, special attention was paid to the necessity of introducing information technologies that fully meet global requirements in all areas of education . Electronic education system creates new opportunities and new tasks. Among the main opportunities are solving educational problems, expanding the choice of the form of education, and increasing the means of knowledge transfer. The need to understand the place and role of digital technologies in modern education should be reflected in modern research in the fields of preschool and primary education methodology and didactics. Among the main opportunities are solving educational problems, expanding the choice of the form of education, and increasing the means of knowledge transfer. The need to understand the place and role of digital technologies in modern education should be reflected in modern research in the fields of preschool education methodology and didactics. Currently, the problems of using digital technologies in the integration of preschool education are the reason for research related to the choice of the future development strategy and direction. Modern digital technologies provide new tools for the development of all educational institutions around the world. Digitization creates opportunities to share lessons learned and knowledge,

empowering people to be more informed and make better decisions in their daily lives. In the near future, there will be major changes in the educational environment related to digitalization. It is clear that a digital transformation program must already be developed in order to move to a competitive education and research model in the future. The problems of the e-learning system can be divided into two classes : current (transitional) and immanent. Today, the rapid penetration of the educational system into digital technologies creates a basis for serious analysis and pedagogical justification of many things presented in the information space. Nowadays, there are a lot of developing interactive systems, computer games, and multimedia products designed for Russian and English-speaking students , and anyone who knows the language can easily use them. Based on the above , it is worth noting that the introduction of digital technologies is very important for the development of the preschool education system, but at the same time, it is necessary to form a scientifically based approach to their implementation. Currently, several projects for the development of this sector are being implemented in our country. The use of information and computer technologies in familiarizing with the rules of the road makes it possible to conduct the lesson in a non-traditional, meaningful way, and to provide various techniques and teaching methods. The use of animation, slide presentations, films allows people to arouse active cognitive interest in the studied phenomena . The methods of visual support of the material allow students to focus their attention for a long time, as well as to affect several sensory organs of the child at the same time, which helps to strengthen the acquired new knowledge more firmly . .

traffic rules:

- mobile, sports, physical exercises; - logical tasks, games - riddles;
- role playing ; - road miniature theater, games - dramatization;
- intellectual and educational games, trips, quizzes; - didactic;
- Printed on the desktop, with objects.

Causes of traffic accidents: At the meeting, the deplorable situation in the field was critically analyzed based on statistical data .

According to the analysis , accidents:.

- 45 percent of drivers disregard the rules;
 - 10 percent of drivers' inexperience;
 - 25 percent of road conditions and infrastructure not meeting the requirements;
- accidents are caused by pedestrians not following the rules .

The use of modern digital technologies in the educational process is very important. Nowadays, using digital technologies in pre-school education and learning the rules of the road is of great importance. In this case , it is very important to teach students about road signs or traffic rules through digital technologies . Thus, the following digital technologies can be used in the preschool education system through modern technologies.

Here are the features of the mobile app :

- no internet is needed, which means there are no extra costs (the driving school is intended to be distributed free of charge to students) and it provides an opportunity to study even in areas where there is a problem with the internet.
- the mobile application is programmed not in the form of a book , but as a presentation, which makes it easier for the student to study.
- the placement of the video after the presentation makes it easier for the audience to learn.

Currently, several projects for the development of this sector are being implemented in our country. In the pre-school education system, electronic multimedia lessons are presented and they are effectively used in the teaching process. The need to move to the digitalization of the educational space is explained by several factors. First, almost all of today's listeners belong to the digital native generation, who show a great inclination to use new technologies in their daily lives. In particular, this applies to IT and Internet technologies, as well as their use not only in the professional sphere, but also for socialization and communication. By instilling the rules of the road in the minds of educators who use mobile applications and manuals in pre-school educational organizations, we would prevent the terrible incidents that occur among the educators through road vehicles.

Conclusion: it must be said that modern digital technologies provide new tools for the development of all educational institutions around the world. Digitization creates opportunities to share lessons learned and knowledge, empowering people to be more informed and make better decisions in their daily lives. In the near future, there will be major changes in the educational environment related to digitalization. At the same time, inculcating traffic rules into the minds of children through modern digital technologies would help the development of the next generation and prevent accidents occurring among children.

References:

- 1.Uzbekistan dated July 11, 2017 No. PQ-3127 "On measures to further improve the road safety system" decision.
- 2.No. 408 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 31, 2018 decision.
- 3.Uzbekistan dated February 23, 2018 decision.
- 4.Pedagogy. Annotated dictionary / O. Askarova, M. Usmonboeva, Kh. Rakhmatova, F. Ehsonova, F. Askarova. – Namangan: NamDU, 2014. – p. 130
- 5.Pedagogical diagnosis and correction/XARakhmatova, - Namangan p. 73-120.
- 6.Khakimov Sh.K and Joraev Ya.R. Electronic training manual on the basics of "Traffic rules and safe driving" for mobile android phones. 2020.
- 7.Usmanova MN An approach to assessing driver skills factors in traffic safety. Bulletin of TADI. Scientific and technical journal. 4.2016 90-93 pp.